

TACKLING HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICT IN NIGERIA’S PROTECTED AREAS.

Human–wildlife conflict (HWC) has been a long-standing threat to the lives and livelihoods of people and wildlife in Nigeria (Fada- et al., 2023; Odunlami et al & Osumenya, V.O., 2020). The problem is widespread across the country, occurring in communities living near major protected areas such as Yankari Game Reserve, Okomu National Park, the Filinga Range of Gashaka Gumti National Park, Kainji Lake National Park, Cross River National Park, Idanre Forest Reserve, Lekki Conservation Centre, Itasin Tropical Swamp Forest, and Old Oyo National Park (Dunn et al., 2024; Wahab et al., 2024; Adeola et al., 2022; Akinsorotan et al., 2021; Digun-Aweto & Van Der Merwe, 2020; Odunlami et al & Osumenya, V.O., 2020; Olaleru, F. & Omotosho, O.O., 2020; Eniang et al., 2011). HWC in these areas follows an escalation pathway and levels (Figure 1). At Level 1 (disputes), wildlife species such as elephants, buffalo, warthogs, and tantalus monkeys frequently encroach into farms and villages, raiding crops and livestock, destroying homes, and causing injuries during human–wildlife encounters and retaliatory clashes (Adeola et al., 2022; Akinsorotan et al., 2021; Odunlami et al & Osumenya, V.O., 2020; Zimmermann et al., 2020). The recurrence of these incidents over time, in the absence of effective resolution, has driven escalation to Level 2 – underlying conflict (Figure 1) (Zimmermann et al., 2020). The impacts on people are immediate and severe, including exposure to zoonotic diseases, loss of income due to crop and livestock damage, physical injuries, and fatalities resulting from wildlife attacks (Magama et al., 2018). In July 2025, Nigerian Tribune, 2025 reported the death of a farmer killed by a migrating elephant in Ogun State and another killed by a hippopotamus in Adamawa State. This persistent human–wildlife conflict fuels negative attitudes and perceptions toward wildlife, contributing to Level 3 (Deep-rooted conflict) (Figure 1) and erodes the support of local and Indigenous communities for conservation projects (Akinsorotan et al., 2021; Zimmermann et al., 2020). Alongside this, species most frequently involved in these conflicts face heightened risks of population decline and local extinction due to retaliatory killings, poisoning, and other lethal responses (FAO, 2009; Distefano, 2005; Ogada et al., 2003). These incidents highlight that human–wildlife conflict is no longer a localized conservation challenge but a growing rural safety, livelihood, and governance concern. Addressing this issue is critical for the Federal Ministry of Environment and State Governments to protect rural communities and biodiversity.

The Levels of Conflict over Wildlife

Figure 1: Levels of conflict over wildlife (Zimmermann et al., 2020).

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. CONSTRUCT PHYSICAL BARRIERS IN PROTECTED AREAS AND FARMLANDS.

Figure 2. A man Setting up a smelly fence (Dunn et al., 2024)

- Erect single live strands electric fences (1.5 meters) above ground around protected areas to halt the passage of wildlife.

- Construct Fences (types: wire gauze, galvanized iron) in the form of trenches dug around farmlands near to protected areas.

- Construct Smelly fences, bee hives fences to scare Elephants from local Farms (Figure 2).

- Construct Chilli Pepper fences to reduce wildlife encroachment.

- Utilize sharp stones to stop Elephants from crossing boundaries.

- Plant species with thorns and spikes should be planted at the boundary to prevent wildlife from encroaching into farms.

2. HARNESS SENSORY AND ACOUSTIC DETERRENTS AND AVERSION SYSTEMS

- Use acoustic noises (shooting, sirens, firecracker, beating drums, and gunshots sound) tape recording to deter predators from farmlands.
- Chemical deterrents such as capsaicin resin from chili pepper should be applied around properties to provoke odour and scare Elephants.
- Make visual deterrents like brightly coloured materials, bright light systems, and scare crow that mimic humans.
- Apply substances to crops and livestock to deter wildlife.

3. CREATE AWARENESS AND ORGANIZE TRAINING AND EDUCATION SCHEMES

- Organize public campaigns (radio, talkshows, meetings and symposiums) for residents of adjoining communities on the methods of avoiding human wildlife conflicts.
- Campaigns to promote peaceful co-existence between humans and wildlife should be organized.
- The management of National parks and other protected areas should organize training on human-wildlife conflict resolution.
- Organize training to educate Game reserves Staff on how to tame trouble animals.
- Enlist local leaders, youths and teach them how to chase wildlife away from farms.

4. UTILIZE TECHNOLOGY, GPS AND EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS.

Figure 3. Farmers in a watchtower at night safeguarding their crops from Elephants (Dunn et al., 2024)

- Use Remote cameras to detect species of concern.
- Recruit active guards to detect wildlife crossing boundaries.
- Use domestic animals like donkeys to guard livestock and farms.
- Reserve workers should be equipped with the latest technology (GPS, satellite imagery system).
- GPS-enabled Elephant collars should be used to monitor the group of elephants movement.
- Set up watch towers and equip the watch guards with phones to report sightings (Figure 3).
- Give farmers a user-friendly toll-free line for quick reporting of wildlife destruction incidents.

5. IMPLEMENT EFFECTIVE COMPENSATION SCHEMES

- Set up timely and fair payment schemes for farmers whose crops were destroyed to avoid retaliation.
- Gather accurate data on the target audience (victims) of crop raidings.
- Use drones and access incidents of crop raidings and initiate compensation quickly.

TECHNICAL REPORT

1. CONSTRUCT PHYSICAL BARRIERS IN PROTECTED AREAS AND FARMLANDS.

In Kenya beehive fences have been successfully used to deter and scare elephants from communities' farmlands (King et al., 2009). These fences exploit elephants' sensitivity to bee stings and represent a low-cost, non-lethal deterrent. In Namibia, sharp stones were used to prevent elephants from crossing boundaries, and stone walls were also used to stop buffalo from raiding agricultural lands (FAO, 2009; Hanks, 2006). Similarly, Dror et al., 2020 reported that a pilot electric fence caused elephants to retreat when approaching fenced areas. These findings agree with IUCN, 2023 which documented that physical exclusion measures can be effective in reducing wildlife incursions in the short term, particularly when barriers are properly installed and maintained. However, the long-term effectiveness and scalability of these interventions remain uncertain. Beehive fences were trialled in Botswana in South Africa, they had limited impact due to difficulties in maintaining active beehives in landscapes with insufficient vegetation to support healthy bee populations (IUCN, 2023). This is to say that the same intervention may produce different outcomes across landscapes, and highlights the importance of understanding the specific ecological and livelihood context in which human-wildlife conflict occurs. Electric fencing also presents significant limitations. Its effectiveness is influenced by land topography and it can restrict wildlife movement, potentially disrupting migration routes, breeding, and reproduction (Digun-Aweto & Van Der Merwe, 2020). Cost is a major constraint: (Muruthi, 2005) estimated that a 3.3 m electric fence cost over USD 20,000 per kilometre in Aberdare National Park, Kenya. In addition, unstable power supply in low and middle-income countries can further limit effectiveness, particularly in rural areas (Digun-Aweto & Van Der Merwe, 2020). In some cases, African elephants have been observed to break electric fences using their tusks and cross boundaries (Mutinda et al., 2014) indicating behavioural adaptation over time. Other physical barriers also have associated risks. Plant species with thorns and spikes used as living fences may spread beyond intended areas and, in some cases, become invasive or act as agricultural pests (Digun-Aweto & Van Der Merwe, 2020). This highlights the need to assess unintended ecological consequences alongside conflict reduction benefits. There are data limitations, including a lack of long-term and West Africa-specific studies assessing the sustained effectiveness of physical barriers. Again, wildlife behaviour can change over time through learning and adaptation. As a result, interventions that are effective at early stages may

become less effective without continuous management (IUCN, 2023). This suggests that while physical barriers can reduce human–wildlife conflict, no single measure is universally effective and suggests that physical barriers should be implemented as context-specific and adaptable interventions, supported by regular monitoring to track effectiveness and respond to emerging limitations.

2. HARNESS SENSORY AND ACOUSTIC DETERRENTS AND AVERSION SYSTEMS

Acoustic deterrents such as sirens, firecrackers, beating drums, and gunshot sounds can scare animals and cause them to leave an area (Götz & Janik 2013). This agrees with the findings in Kenya, where acoustic sounds have been used to deter elephants from farmlands (Odunlami et al & Osumenya, V.O., 2020). Visual deterrents, including brightly coloured materials, flamboyant clothing, and scarecrows that mimic human presence, were reported to be successful in Chuchera National Park, Ethiopia (Datiko & Bekele, 2013), and have also been used to reduce wildlife encroachment into farmlands in other contexts (Adams et al., 2020; Ohrens et al., 2019). These findings suggest that sensory deterrents can be effective, particularly in agricultural landscapes adjacent to protected areas. Across these studies, there is a common agreement that acoustic, visual, and chemical deterrents can reduce wildlife incursions in the short term by provoking avoidance responses. Chemical deterrents such as capsaicin resin obtained from chilli pepper have been shown to repel elephants due to their irritating effect on contact (FAO, 2009). This is consistent with earlier studies of Osborn, 2002 which reported that chemical deterrents applied around properties can repel wild animals and reduce damage. However, the durability and safety of these interventions is uncertain. Applying substances to crops or livestock can reduce damage (IUCN, 2023), but may cause undesirable effects such as illness if consumed by wildlife. Studies also indicate that wildlife may learn to avoid treated crops after initial exposure (Baker et al., 2008), suggesting that effectiveness may decline over time. Many studies assess short-term responses, with limited long-term monitoring to evaluate sustained effectiveness. Again, as animals may habituate to repeated acoustic or visual stimuli and see it as ‘empty threat’ (IUCN, 2023). Hence, sensory and acoustic deterrents should be applied as adaptive, context-specific measures and monitored to assess continued effectiveness.

3. CREATE AWARENESS AND ORGANIZE TRAINING AND EDUCATION SCHEMES

Following warthog raids on farmlands near Old Oyo National Park, conservation education interventions were implemented and it achieved a moderate effectiveness of approximately 60% in reducing impacts on farm income (Wahab et al. 2024). This suggests that education and awareness programmes can influence community behaviour and responses to wildlife incursions. This is in agreement with Odunlami et al & Osumenya, V.O., 2020 which reported that conservation education initiatives improves community attitudes toward wildlife and supports

peaceful co-existence between humans and wildlife. Training and capacity-building for protected area staff have also been identified as important components of conflict management. Magama et al. 2018 found that equipping reserve workers with training and modern wildlife-tracking technologies improved their ability to monitor and manage animal movements, particularly during migration periods. This supports the role of targeted training in strengthening institutional responses to human–wildlife conflict. Across these studies, there is a general consensus that awareness creation and training can reduce conflict risks by improving knowledge, preparedness, and response capacity. However, uncertainties persist regarding the extent to which education alone can produce sustained reductions in conflict without complementary physical or deterrent measures. Most studies assess short-term or site-specific outcomes, with limited evaluation of long-term behavioural change among communities or wildlife. In addition, education-based interventions are subject to contextual uncertainty, as their effectiveness depends on local participation, institutional support, and sustained engagement. This indicates that awareness creation and training schemes are most effective when implemented as supporting measures alongside other conflict mitigation strategies, rather than as standalone solutions.

4. UTILIZE TECHNOLOGY, GPS AND EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS.

GPS-enabled elephant collars have been reported to be effective in monitoring the movement of elephant groups and reducing crop-raiding incidents (Odunlami et al & Osumenya, V.O., 2020). This agrees with Weise et al., 2019 claim that GPS-collared wildlife linked to alarm systems can detect when animals cross designated boundaries, enabling rapid response by guards and communities. Remote camera systems have also been shown to detect species of concern and support early warning and monitoring efforts (IUCN, 2023). Evidence from Indonesia demonstrates the effectiveness of early warning and crop-guarding systems when community participation is high. In Way Kambas National Park India, 16 villages repelled 150 out of 202 attempted elephant raids, while 7 villages successfully repelled 100% of attempted raids using crop guarding and low-technology and early warning approaches (Gunaryadi et al., 2017) as shown in figure 4. This indicates that surveillance and early warning systems can substantially reduce wildlife incursions when adequately implemented. Hence, technology-supported by early warning systems improve detection and response capacity and can reduce labour costs associated with constant guarding. However, their impact differs depending on context. For example, crop guarding in the Nakai Plateau, Laos, was unsuccessful due to low community participation, equipment theft, and insufficient patrolling of field boundaries. (IUCN, 2023). This suggests that an intervention effective in one context may not necessarily succeed in another. A clear understanding of local socio-ecological conditions is therefore essential to ensure the adaptability and appropriateness of proposed actions. Context-specific assessment can enhance effectiveness and inform evidence-based decisions on whether an intervention should be implemented, adapted, or not pursued at all (IUCN, 2023). There is uncertainty in the evidence primarily from contextual and institutional factors, including variability in community participation, maintenance capacity, and governance structures. In addition, there is data uncertainty, as many

studies are site-specific and short-term, limiting understanding of long-term effectiveness. While GPS-based systems may reduce opportunity costs associated with labour-intensive guarding, technology alone is insufficient and must be complemented by social and institutional support mechanisms (IUCN, 2023). This suggests that technology, GPS, and early warning systems are most effective when implemented as context-specific, integrated measures, rather than standalone solutions, and when supported by sustained monitoring and local engagement.

Village	No. of attempted elephant raids (3 July 2008 to 25 March 2009)	No. of raids not repelled	No. of raids repelled	Proportion of raids repelled successfully
Braja Asri	43	9	34	79.1%
Braja Yekti	7	0	7	100.0%
Labuhan Ratu IX	7	3	4	57.1%
Labuhan Ratu VI	40	17	23	57.5%
Labuhan Ratu VII	19	10	9	47.4%
Muara Jaya	6	4	2	33.3%
Raja Basa Lama I	10	5	5	50.0%
Rantau Jaya Udik II	5	2	3	60.0%
Sidodadi	1	0	1	100.0%
Taman Fajar	11	1	10	90.9%
Tambah Dadi	3	0	3	100.0%
Tanjung Kesuma	3	0	3	100.0%
Tanjung Tirto	2	0	2	100.0%
Tegal Ombo	19	0	19	100.0%
Tegal Yoso	24	2	22	91.7%
Totoprojo	3	0	3	100.0%
Grand total	203	53	150	73.9%

Figure 4: Percentage of elephant raid attempts deterred by voluntary community-based crop guarding methods in 16 villages near Way Kambas National Park (Gunaryadi et al., 2017).

5. IMPLEMENT EFFECTIVE COMPENSATION SCHEMES

Compensation schemes have been widely applied to offset losses from crop raiding and livestock depredation (Johnson et al., 2018; Watve et al., 2016, Ogra & Badola, 2008). This is an agreement with IUCN, 2023 that compensation can reduce immediate economic burdens on affected farmers and serve as a mechanism for addressing human–wildlife conflict impacts. However, many studies highlight significant implementation challenges. Compensation schemes often fail to reach actual victims, provide insufficient payments, or are captured by more affluent

community members (Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017; Hoare, 2012). These limitations reduce their effectiveness and credibility. While compensation may deliver short-term benefits, it can generate limited long-term outcomes by reinforcing perceptions that wildlife management is solely the responsibility of external agencies (Digun-Aweto & Van Der Merwe, 2020). Oftentimes, compensation schemes have been criticized for not giving suitable compensation to the victims (Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017; Hoare, 2012). Timeliness and reliability are consistently identified as critical determinants of scheme performance. Delayed or unreliable payments have been shown to reduce claimant support and undermine participation (IUCN, 2023; Anthony, 2021). These findings suggest that accurate identification of affected households and rapid assessment of crop-raiding incidents are necessary to improve effectiveness. Uncertainty remains due to context-specific outcomes and governance constraints, indicating that compensation should be carefully designed and implemented alongside clear verification and accountability mechanisms.

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